

The web paradigm, where digital assets are linked to one another into an information-rich maze across which computation moves freely, is a fitting metaphor for the new space that will result from AI-augmented weaving of future IoT and CPS nodes into a seamless continuum with the cloud. The new web that will emerge will be spatially aware, allowing humans to relate to it in a manner more akin to their perception of the physical world and their mental representation of it.

The “next web”

Weaving future IoT and CPS into an AI-augmented, spatially aware, digital-and-physical space

By TULLIO VARDANEGA

The term “internet of things” (IoT) evokes the interconnection of networks of compute devices that reach out to the physical world across geographical expanses, for sensing and actuating physical “things”, thereby providing compute-based intelligence to physical environments in the real world. If we take the ‘I’ of the IoT to mean the internet for real, then it would be natural to extend the analogy even further.

In the internet space, in fact, the web (combined with the cloud, which firmly rests on the web) has long become the most convenient and practical platform for accessing digital resources, as well as for using, deploying, and developing applications. From that perspective, therefore, the modern web may be regarded as a ubiquitous programmable space, available to anyone, anywhere, any time.

This vision argues that future IoT systems may be imagined as the “next web” space, where every “thing” is reachable as a linked digital resource, and applications are programmed, deployed and used in an “as-a-service” mode, located on the device(s) where that is more convenient to the end user. Future IoT systems will weave into a seamless continuum with the cyber-physical systems (CPS) space, where command-and-control capabilities add to sensing and actuation at the border between the physical and the digital world. Artificial intelligence (AI) will permeate the whole digital space in order for it to engage satisfactorily with the human side.

This compute-intensive evolution of the digital space, from the extreme edge, where the physical world begins, to the centre of the cloud, farthest from it, will give rise to a single unified continuum of computing, bringing along with it an array of technological, social and ethical challenges. In order for the web paradigm to adapt to this transformation, it will have to incorporate spatial awareness, with proximity, locality, and positioning in space and time becoming important attributes of digital assets, necessitating the adaptation of technology and protocols.

Key insights

- In the light of the modern web metaphor, the future IoT may be likened to a programmable space where applications are dynamic aggregates of components residing anywhere, deployed and used in an as-a-service mode, with a centre of execution determined as the most convenient to the user requirements.
- The aggregation of disparate service components and resources should be regarded as a personalized orchestration. Its execution engine must be trusted to abide by user preferences, while it should be able to withstand malicious infiltrations/deflections and privacy-breaking intrusions. It should also be vendor neutral and maximally interoperable.

- Programming orchestrators should evolve from traditional manual coding to modes that include “natural programming”, where the human user employs natural interfaces (voice, audio, context) to express needs, objectives and requirements, and an intelligent engine turns such input into program code.
- Conceivably, such orchestrators may be further organized into an autonomous conversational hierarchical assembly, where an orchestrator may seek help from or provide support to others, in the quest to satisfy user requirements.
- Interoperability is a central prerequisite to the enactment of this vision. Achieving this will require various levels of standards, from specification and pro-

gramming abstractions to interaction and networking protocols.

- The command-and-control element of cyber-physical systems will weave into the new web space, bringing about technological, social and ethical requirements for AI-augmented seamless interaction between humans and digital assets.
- The increasingly blurred border between the digital and the human sides of the compute continuum will cause the new web to become increasingly more physical. Instead of going *on* the web, we humans will be going *into* a new “spatial” web.

Key recommendations

- Research and development actions should be launched to explore the realization of web-inspired re-interpretation of future IoT systems.
- Proof-of-concept level efforts should be launched to develop agreed definitions of functional and non-functional specifications and accompanying programming support for execution- and communication-level interoperability across the continuum of computing.

- Promote demonstrative testbeds of “trusted orchestrators”, running on any mobile device and appliance to serve the needs of safe, private, personalized and effective service composition on the computing continuum.
- Explore ways to enable “AI at the edge” and weave it with cloud intelligence in a manner that provides for rapid feedback cycles to actions and events occurring in the compute continuum.

- Devise low-latency, multi-modal, reliable communication architectures following the tactile internet paradigm to support peer-to-peer seamless interactions among humans and digital assets in the compute continuum.
- Promote the realization of “world model” pilots that showcase impactful uses of the spatial web, for example for decarbonization scenarios.
- Provide active support to standardization efforts toward the spatial web.

Premise

The basic component-level ingredients of modern IoT systems are becoming increasingly easy to use, both as individual items and amateur-style (introductory) collections *within vertical integrations* within the strict bounds of a single ecosystem (make/supplier). House automation is one of the most typifying examples of this tendency, where amateur users can set up complete commodity-level installations with very little hassle, so long as the components are from one and the same technology vendor.

At the same time, however, it can be observed that modern IoT systems at industrial/professional scale are becoming increasingly complex to build, master, evolve (and use). This is due to overwhelming heterogeneity in the available hardware and software components, including for

end-user apps, which massively overlap for functionality, and expose / use extremely different APIs.

We anticipate that the next level of digitalization will result in a “maze of IoT”. This could be built either statically (as permanent, stable aggregations), or dynamically (as opportunistic, temporary aggregations). We therefore need to address the technical challenges that arise from the effort to enact this vision.

Overarching vision

As future IoT systems become increasingly programmable, they also weave into a seamless continuum with the cyber-physical systems space, where command-and-control capabilities add to sensing and actuation at the border between the physical and the digital world. This convergence calls for AI to permeate the digital space in

order for it to engage satisfactorily with the human side. This compute-intensive evolution will cause the whole digital space, from the extreme edge, where the physical world begins, to the centre of the cloud, which is farthest from it, to morph into a single continuum of computing, with an array of technological, social and ethical challenges to be addressed in that transformation.

The increasingly blurred border between the digital and the human sides of the compute continuum will cause the new web to become increasingly more physical. Instead of going on the web, we humans will be going into a new web, which we call “spatial” in this HiPEAC Vision chapter, to signify the need for it to recognize physical space (with proximity, locality, and positioning in space and time becoming key additional attributes of assets). Some enterprise projects have put forward their own

(controversial) interpretations of this new space and coined the term “metaverse” for it. An article in this chapter reflects on the human side, for motivations, requirements, and anticipated obstacles of the envisioned transition into an AI-augmented, spatially aware digital universe.

The convergence of autonomous vehicles, drones and bots, IoT sensors, augmented reality, sovereign identity, digital transactions, ubiquitous high-speed connectivity, and AI-augmented orchestration calls for new low-latency and interoperable technologies and standard protocols.

From human-expert mediation to trustworthy software orchestration

One such advancement should radically change the way one may go from actual needs (user requirements, whether industrial or individual, to component selection (equivalent to design) and integration (equivalent to system build). This route should no longer be an expert-only task, because obligatory human-expert mediation in such endeavours is an intrinsic bottleneck, a painful vulnerability, and a tremendous slow-down factor.

It should be replaced by a trustworthy “software mediator”, capable of supporting natural interfaces (voice, drawing, gestures, context, examples), therefore conducive to “natural programming” Indeed, there is a potential link between this requirement and the capabilities of the low-code/no-code app development techniques. Those two paradigms might be the lower-end of the accomplishment of our vision, but we really anticipate going beyond them, in a manner that takes inspiration from the Codex and CodePilot initiatives, in which the human intervention is limited to the specification side and not to assembling code. The way such software mediators should operate for transforming user needs into programmatic artefacts may leverage the impressive advancements in the field of “natural-language-to-code” translators such as OpenAI Codex [1].

This notion of automated software mediator has one distinct premise and two distinct implications.

The premise is that much / most of what is needed to satisfy the end-user needs already exists in the form of partial solutions, which only need to be glued together in a functionally sound, solid (robust and scalable) and seamless workflow. Checking for availability can be done by periodically crawling registered repositories, whose authors have agreed to be part of the “project” and are consequently offered a sufficiently informative manifest file, previously screened to ensure sufficient quality.

The two implications concern the nature of the resulting “product” (the trustworthy software mediator).

- First, human interaction with the envisioned natural interfaces may be regarded as the “next web”. In fact, the human-in-the-loop mode of operation may be regarded as the base of a hierarchy of interaction models that, as one goes up it, allow for progressively more autonomous inter-orchestrator dialogue, which eventually only needs humans for final approval. All of the resources of interest (digital assets of all kinds, many of which are increasingly “digital twins” of physical artefacts connected to the IoT system) should be navigable, linkable, CRUD-ready (within obvious limits of ownership and privacy of access) from a uniform-unified-omnipresent interface, much as we have become accustomed to when navigating the internet strictly over the web and interacting with all kinds of digital resources exposed in the web space, in two-way directions. By CRUD-ready, we mean digital entities that can be created, read, used, and deleted by a simple unified programming interface, which is the web interface itself [2].

The technical name of the logical (virtual) platform underneath this “next web” is the “continuum of computing”, which allows data and code to move freely, wherever most appropriate for reasons of privacy, energy, latency, capacity, etc. The realization of such a platform requires vertical and horizontal cross-stack interoperability, which is not only technical but also semantical.

- Second, the entity that does produce and execute the workflow designated to satisfy user needs may be regarded as an “orchestrator” capable of residing at the edge, as near as possible to the end user. This entity is an orchestrator because it deploys, executes, controls, and maintains the functional workflow that carries out the required (service) job.

In concept, this orchestrator is analogous to, but considerably more powerful than, recent “infrastructure-as-code” (IaC) engines that are transforming cloud deployment procedures from the recipe-based declarative manifests of the recent past to outright programmatic ones, massively raising the power of abstraction and algorithmic logic in the corresponding specifications. The term “infrastructure-as-code” designates a technical solution of application deployment in the cloud that is realized programmatically – by a true program, written in a cloud-native programming language – instead of declaratively by way of a manifest-like “recipe”. The difference between the two modalities is that the former is far richer in expressive power than the latter and therefore naturally conducive to realizing sophisticated deployment policies that cover the entire application life cycle in all circumstances, including scaling-

Figure 1: Adaption from Philippe Sayegh’s presentation at IoT Week (21 June 2022)

out and scaling-in situations, mitigation procedures, etc. The envisioned orchestrators are more powerful than those IaC engines because they interact via natural interfaces, and because they are most rigorously built as a “trusted code base”, free from the risk of intrusion, hijacking, vendor lock-in, and subservience to malicious intent.

Naturally, the envisioned orchestrators should also play a defensive and protective role toward their user, by shielding them from unwanted interactions, instructions, attacks, and by proactively and responsibly following their preferences for functionality, provenance, ethical concerns, etc.

Everything-as-a-service

Another important game-changing technical objective is to move, in a conscientious, ethical and sustainable way, toward an “everything-as-service” (XaaS) trustworthy distributed platform-and-delivery mode. In this mode, all of the physical world can be interacted with, for use and control, in opportunistic, cross-sectorial, dynamic and highly-scalable aggregations. The main software “intelligence” (the orchestrator evoked under the previous heading) would run on the edge under direct ownership of the end user, instead of being secluded proprietarily deep down in the centre of the cloud. That arrangement would earn obvious yet crucial benefits for transparency, data privacy, and bandwidth reduction. It should be noted that this XaaS notion is a 1:1 match with the notion of “next web” discussed above and the associated corollary of the continuum of computing.

Another important challenge to overcome in order to implement this vision occurs at the hardware- and software-component level: too many important details are hidden away or ignored (notably non-functional, like execution time, response latency, predictability, energy balance, interaction with the external environment) in the current programming technology.

To overcome that deficiency, at the development level, we need more unifying abstractions (for algorithms and data structures, for programming artefacts, for cross-stack services).

The race for the “next web”

Various visions for a more interactive, intuitive “next web” have emerged, some of which reflect the priorities of a narrow section of extremely powerful, mostly US-based technology giants. In order to create a future web that properly serves its users, it is important to define possibilities, prerequisites and potential pitfalls of any particular scenario.

The articles in this section explore different aspects relating to the creation of this “next web” paradigm:

- **“Digels, digital genius loci engines to guide and protect users in the ‘next web’”.** This article presents the concept of the “Digel”, a trustable, protective guide capable of orchestrating the “next web” and providing a seamless experience for users.
- **“The spatial web: Interconnecting people, places, things and AI for a smarter world”.** This article presents the concept of the “spatial web”, the next evolution in computing and information technology, which will eventually eliminate the boundary between digital content and physical objects.
- **“Defining cyber-physical systems: Large-scale safety-critical systems”.** This article presents a definition of cyber-physical systems (CPS) from the application perspective. It classifies CPS requirements and points to future directions for research.
- **“Bridging the stakeholder communities that produce cyber-physical systems”.** This article provides a detailed outline of the different communities involved in producing cyber-physical systems (CPS), and emphasizes the importance of bringing these communities together.
- **“Towards a living dimension: The future of cyber-physical systems”.** This article explores the technical ingredients for future cyber-physical systems, including artificial intelligence, the tactile internet, swarm behaviour and the compute continuum. It outlines future challenges and suggests how Europe could meet these.
- **“Gaming, content and the metaverse”.** This article explores trends in augmented reality and simulation, and provides suggestions of how Europe should participate in the future “metaverse”.

Figure 2: The multiple dimensions of the capabilities to be provided for in the realization of this vision. (This picture is drawn from an EU-US joint white paper that overlaps the topics addressed by this vision document).

- **“EU/US joint effort on the continuum of computing”.** This article presents the results of recent discussions between European Union (EU) researchers and representatives of the United States National Science Foundation. It outlines the technical challenges and envisioned directions for the evolution of the compute continuum.

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